

Assessment of Drug Use Pattern Among Patients Visiting Ambulatory Patient Education Centre of a Tertiary Care Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Drug-Related Problems (DRPs) are widespread in psychiatric care due to complex pharmacotherapy, polypharmacy, and coexisting conditions. The chronic nature of mental diseases frequently necessitates long-term medication, raising the risk of DRPs such as ADRs, interactions, and incorrect dose. These concerns can result in longer hospital stays, increased morbidity, and higher healthcare expenses. DRPs are defined by the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe as events that prevent desirable health outcomes from occurring. Clinical pharmacists play an important role in recognizing, preventing, and managing DRPs to improve patient safety and therapeutic efficacy. **Objective:** The aim of this study was to determine the incidence and types of drug-related problems (DRPs) among psychiatric patients. Specific objectives included assessing drug use using WHO prescribing indicators, looking into the kind and prevalence of DRPs and ADRs, and identifying important risk factors. The goal was to increase pharmaceutical safety while maximizing therapeutic efficacy. **Methodology:** A prospective interventional study was carried out over nine months in the psychiatry department of JSS Hospital in Mysuru. Patients admitted to the psychiatric ward and on at least two drugs were included. The required data including the patient's socio demographic details, medical history, present illness, were gathered from treatment chart, patient interviews, and interactions with healthcare providers were done. DRPs were classified using the Hepler and Strand categorization approach. Adverse drug responses (ADRs) were evaluated using the WHO-UMC causality assessment and Naranjo's procedure. Lexicomp (UpToDate) was used to examine drug interactions and categorize them according to their severity. Drug use patterns were assessed using WHO core prescription indicators. **Result:** Of the 228 participants, 73.6% were male, and the most common age group was 31-40 years (42%). Comorbid conditions were found in 25.87% of patients, with hypertension and diabetes being the most prevalent. A total of 1,777 drugs were prescribed, with an average of 7.79 drugs per patient, indicating significant polypharmacy. Only 8.8% of drugs were prescribed by generic name, and 76.47% were from the Essential Drug List. A total of 265 DRPs were identified, the most frequent being drug-drug interactions (58.86%), untreated indications (13.2%), and ADRs (9.81%). ADRs were primarily associated with antipsychotics and benzodiazepines, with constipation being the most reported reaction. DRPs were significantly associated with comorbidities ($p < 0.0001$) and social history ($p = 0.0115$), while age and gender showed no significant association. **Conclusion:** This study emphasizes the significant occurrence of DRPs among psychiatric patients, which is caused by polypharmacy, comorbidities, and the complex nature of psychiatric pharmacotherapy. The majority of DRPs were preventable, and clinical pharmacist involvement significantly enhanced the identification and management. The study highlights pharmacists' vital role in encouraging rational drug usage, lowering ADRs, and maintaining medication safety. Implementing structured clinical pharmacy services, regular medication reviews, and organized interdisciplinary practices are critical for reducing DRPs in psychiatric settings and improving patient outcomes.

Keywords: Drug-related problems (DRPs), psychiatric disorders, clinical pharmacist, pharmacovigilance, adverse drug reactions (ADRs), polypharmacy, psychiatric inpatients, WHO prescribing indicators, Hepler and Strand classification, medication safety.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Pharmaceutical Care Network of Europe (PCNE), a Drug-Related Problem (DRP) is

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“An event or circumstance involving drug therapy that actually or potentially interferes with desired health outcomes”. DRPs are important problems in healthcare systems worldwide, associated with patient harm and increased economic burden. Drug therapy is growing more complex, thus making appropriate patient management increasingly challenging. DRPs can occur at all steps of the treatment process, mainly during prescribing, transcribing, and dispensing. Most of them can be preventable by pharmaceutical care services. DRPs more frequently occur in hospitalized patients who have multiple changes in medication regimens, and they are commonly found in internal medicine wards, especially in university hospitals due to the complexity of patient care. They are primary concerns that arise during drug therapy, potentially hindering desired clinical outcomes across various patient populations. These problems are prevalent in both pediatric and elderly patients, as well as in intensive care settings, highlighting the need for effective management strategies. These problems can be actual or potential, meaning they may have already occurred or could occur in the future. DRPs are a common occurrence in both primary and tertiary care settings around the world. Addressing DRPs requires a comprehensive understanding of pharmacotherapy, patient characteristics, and environmental factors. Unpredictability arises when a drug product produces an unwanted side effect that has nothing to do with dosage. Effective identification and resolution of these problems can lead to improved adherence to treatment regimens and enhanced therapeutic efficacy.

The risk of these problems increases with the number of drugs. Polypharmacy, defined as the use of more than four or five drugs, occurs in 40% of the adults over 65 years old. Prevalence of polypharmacy reaches up to 90% of adults over 75 years at the moment of hospital admission. Besides, during hospitalization, drug changes and new medicines for acute health problems will pose a higher risk of negative health outcomes. Up to 40% of hospitalized patients suffer from drug-related problems. Although DRPs fall into a variety of categories, they are typically associated with therapy efficacy and/or safety. Unresolved or potential DRPs could lead to unnecessary outpatient visits, hospital admissions, and long-term care, which not only interfered with

clinical treatment but also increased patients' financial burden. In brief, DRPs have caused damage to patients' physical health and quality of life to a certain extent and have led to a significant waste of health care resources. Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Association 2020, which mainly includes unnecessary drug treatment, inadequate drug treatment, ineffective drug treatment, adverse drug event, inappropriate dosage, and poor adherence. There are a number of consequences associated with DRPs which include hospitalizations, long-term care admissions, emergency department visits, additional physician office visits, and additional prescriptions. DRPs are a major area concern of the patient's physical, psychological and economic burden to the patients as well as to the whole society. Hence, improving drug therapy by preventing drug-related problems may have an important effect on the patients' health, treatment related costs, potentially save lives and enhance patients' quality of life. Pharmaceutical care is a key strategy to identify and resolve DRPs. Pharmacist plays a key role in minimizing drug related problem through proper use of medicines as most of the errors occur due to scarcity of drug information. The demand of Clinical Pharmacist is increasing rapidly in the health care System.

Pharmacists' participation in medical rounding teams in general wards has contributed to a significant reduction in preventable adverse drug events. Clinical pharmacy services and pharmacy staffing are associated with reduced mortality rates, Pharmacist intervention may have a positive effect on the length of hospital stay, number of adverse drug events, and drug-related readmissions. Intervention is defined as a step taken by pharmacist to optimize the therapeutic management in order to enhance the quality of patient care. Any necessary interventions are implemented to optimize an evidence-based pharmacy care plan. Patients are monitored prospectively on a daily basis throughout their hospitalization. As part of the standard patient care procedure, treatment charts are carefully evaluated to detect any medication-related issues. The detected DRPs are then reviewed and categorized using Hepler and Strand's classification of medication-related problems, ensuring a systematic approach to improving patient safety and therapeutic outcomes. DRP was classified into 8 main categories according to helper-strand classification such as

untreated indication, improper drug selection, subtherapeutic dosage, overdosage, adverse drug reaction, failure to receive drugs, drug interaction, drug use without an indication. Where as Untreated Indication is a medical condition that requires drug therapy but is not being treated with any medication, improper drug selection is a situation where the wrong drug is prescribed, which may be ineffective or inappropriate for the patient's condition, subtherapeutic dosage is the dosage of a prescribed drug is too low to produce the intended therapeutic effect, overdosage is the dosage of a drug is too high, potentially causing toxicity or harmful effects, adverse drug reaction (ADR) is any response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function, Failure to Receive Drugs is the patient does not receive the medication due to various reasons like non-adherence, administration errors, or supply issues, Drug-drug Interaction is where one drug affects the activity of another drug when both are administered together, which may lead to increased toxicity or decreased efficacy, Drug use without an indication is the use of a drug when there is no valid medical reason or condition justifying its administration. The Lexicomp severity rating was used to categorize drug-drug interactions into three groups: "major" interactions, which indicate interactions with a high risk of serious adverse outcomes; "moderate" interactions, which require drug therapy monitoring; and "minor" interactions, which do not require intervention. The cause of all reported adverse drug reactions (ADRs) was assessed using Naranjo's algorithm methodology and the World Health Organization- Uppsala Monitoring Centre causality evaluation scale. Clinical pharmacists performing medication reviews as part of their role. The documentation of pharmacist intervention and assessment of the potential impact of this intervention are necessary for the further development and retention of clinical pharmacists. Clinical pharmacists have an important role in healthcare teams to improve patient care by supporting drug therapy management. Several studies have shown that clinical pharmacists play an essential role in acute care for resolving DRPs, including cost-saving. Understanding the characteristics of DRPs may provide implementation to improve clinical

pharmacy services. The number of drug-related problems (DRP) increased with the number of drugs used. Pharmaceutical care, described as the pharmacist's contribution to the care of individuals in order to optimize medicines use and improve health outcomes, is the foundation of clinical pharmacy

A psychiatric disorder, is a condition that affects a person's thinking, feeling, behavior, or mood and often impacts their ability to function in daily life. It is usually associated with distress or impairment in important areas of functioning. There are many different types of mental disorders. Mental disorders may also be referred to as mental health conditions According to the World Health Organization (WHO),

Mental health is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community. These disorders cause disturbance to the person's mental health and are generally characterized by a combination of abnormal thoughts, perceptions, emotions, behavior and relationships with others Family history of mental illness, stressful life situations, chronic medical conditions, low socio-economic status, substance abuse and alcohol consumption are certain risk factors that predispose individuals of developing a mental illness or psychiatric disorders Pharmacotherapy along with the psychotherapy plays a very important role in the management of psychiatric disorders and provides a great opportunity for people with mental and behavioral disorders and their families to lead full and productive life Untreated mental illness can cause severe emotional, behavioral and physical health problems. Complications sometimes linked to mental illness include, Unhappiness and decreased enjoyment of life, Family conflicts, Relationship difficulties, Social isolation, Problems with tobacco, alcohol and other drugs, Missed work or school, or other problems related to work or school, Legal and financial problems, Poverty and homelessness, self-harm and harm to others, including suicide or homicide, Weakened immune system, so your body has a hard time resisting infections, Heart disease and other medical conditions

Types of Psychiatric disorders include:

Anxiety Disorders are characterized by excessive fear and worry and related behavioral disturbances. Symptoms are severe enough to result in significant distress or significant impairment in functioning. There are several different kinds of anxiety disorders, such as: generalized anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive worry), panic disorder (characterized by panic attacks), social anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive fear and worry in social situations), separation anxiety disorder (characterized by excessive fear or anxiety about separation from those individuals to whom the person has a deep emotional bond), and others. Effective psychological treatment exists, and depending on the age and severity, medication may also be considered.

Below are some examples of anxiety disorders.

Generalized anxiety disorder involves excessive worry or fear that disrupts everyday living. People may also experience physical symptoms, including: restlessness, fatigue, poor concentration, tense muscles, interrupted sleep. They may experience excessive anxiety when encountering everyday situations that do not pose a direct danger, such as chores or appointments. A person with GAD may sometimes feel anxiety with no trigger at all.

Depression is different from usual mood fluctuations and short-lived emotional responses to challenges in everyday life. During a depressive episode, the person experiences depressed mood (feeling sad, irritable, empty) or a loss of pleasure or interest in activities, for most of the day, nearly every day, for at least two weeks. Several other symptoms are also present, which may include poor concentration, feelings of excessive guilt or low self-worth, hopelessness about the future, thoughts about dying or suicide, disrupted sleep, changes in appetite or weight, and feeling especially tired or low in energy. People with depression are at an increased risk of suicide. Yet, effective psychological treatment exists, and depending on the age and severity, medication may also be considered.

Bipolar affective Disorder: A person with bipolar disorder experiences unusual changes. Trusted Source in their mood, energy levels, levels of activity, and ability to continue with daily life. Periods of high mood are known as manic phases, while depressive

phases bring on low mood. During a depressive episode, the person experiences depressed mood (feeling sad, irritable, empty) or a loss of pleasure or interest in activities, for most of the day, nearly every day. Manic symptoms may include euphoria or irritability, increased activity or energy, and other symptoms such as increased talkativeness, racing thoughts, increased self-esteem, decreased need for sleep, distractibility, and impulsive reckless behaviour. People with bipolar disorder are at an increased risk of suicide. Yet effective treatment options exist including psycho-education, reduction of stress and strengthening of social functioning, and medication.

Alcohol dependence syndrome (ADS) is defined by the International Classification of Diseases as the presence of three or more indicators of dependence for at least a month within the previous year. The co-occurrence of substance abuse and mental illness has been known for long. Alcoholics are reported to be three times more likely to suffer from another psychiatric disorder. The risk of development of an alcohol use disorder increases with the frequency of binge drinking, although most heavy drinkers do not meet the criteria for alcohol dependence.

Symptoms

Alcohol use disorder can be mild, moderate or severe, based on the number of symptoms you experience. Signs and symptoms may include:

- Being unable to limit the amount of alcohol you drink
- Wanting to cut down on how much you drink or making unsuccessful attempts to do so
- Spending a lot of time drinking, getting alcohol or recovering from alcohol use
- Feeling a strong craving or urge to drink alcohol
- Failing to fulfill major obligations at work, school or home due to repeated alcohol use
- Continuing to drink alcohol even though you know it's causing physical, social, work or relationship problems

- Giving up or reducing social and work activities and hobbies to use alcohol
- Using alcohol in situations where it's not safe, such as when driving or swimming
- Developing a tolerance to alcohol so you need more to feel its effect or you have a reduced effect from the same amount
- Experiencing withdrawal symptoms such as nausea, sweating and shaking when you don't drink, or drinking to avoid these symptoms

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD): The prevalence of PTSD and other mental disorders is high in conflict-affected settings. PTSD may develop following exposure to an extremely threatening or horrific event or series of events. It is characterized by all of the following:

- 1) Re-experiencing the traumatic event or events in the present (intrusive memories, flashbacks, or nightmares)
- 2) Avoidance of thoughts and memories of the event(s), or avoidance of activities, situations, or people reminiscent of the event(s); and
- 3) Persistent perceptions of heightened current threat. These symptoms persist for at least several weeks and cause significant impairment in functioning. Effective psychological treatment exists.

Schizophrenia: People with schizophrenia have a life expectancy 10-20 years below that of the general population. Schizophrenia is characterized by significant impairments in perception and changes in behaviour. Symptoms may include persistent delusions, hallucinations, disorganized thinking, highly disorganized behaviour, or extreme agitation. People with schizophrenia may experience persistent difficulties with their cognitive functioning. Yet, a range of effective treatment options exist, including medication, psycho-education, family interventions, and psycho-social rehabilitation.

Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD): People with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) may experience constant, stressful thoughts and an urge to perform repetitive acts, such as hand-washing.

Treatment: Various methods are available to help manage mental health conditions. Treatment is highly individual, and what works for one person may not work for another. Some strategies or treatments are more successful in combination with others. A person with a mental health disorder may choose different options at various stages in their life.

Psychotherapy: Psychotherapy, also called talk therapy, involves talking about your condition and related issues with a mental health professional. The following types of therapy Trusted Source take a psychological approach to treating mental health:

- **Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT)** is a therapy technique that aims to help people find new ways to behave by changing their thought patterns. Therapists may use strategies such as role-playing and assigning homework.
- **Exposure therapy** is a type of psychological therapy that can help people overcome their fears or anxiety disorders. It can help reduce feelings of anxiety, distress, or fear that a person may have due to a disorder or previous trauma.
- **Dialectical behavior therapy** helps people tolerate and regulate their emotions. It is based on cognitive behavioral principles and focuses on problem solving and acceptance.

Medication: Some people Trusted Source take prescribed medications, such as antidepressants, antipsychotics, and drugs for anxiety.

Although these medications cannot cure mental health disorders, some can help improve symptoms. They may also help a person to manage their social interactions and routines.

Some of the most commonly used classes of prescription psychiatric medications include

Antidepressants. Antidepressants are used to treat depression, anxiety and sometimes other conditions. They can help improve symptoms such as sadness, hopelessness, lack of energy, difficulty concentrating and lack of interest in activities. Antidepressants are not addictive and do not cause dependency.

Eg; Sertraline, escitalopram, amitriptyline, duloxetine

Anti-anxiety medications. These drugs are used to treat anxiety disorders, such as generalized anxiety disorder or panic disorder. They may also help reduce agitation and insomnia. Long-term anti-anxiety drugs typically are antidepressants that also work for anxiety. Fast-acting anti-anxiety drugs help

with short-term relief, but they also have the potential to cause dependency, so ideally they'd be used short term.

Eg; Clonazepam, lorazepam

Mood-stabilizing medications. Mood stabilizers are most commonly used to treat bipolar disorders, which involves alternating episodes of mania and depression. Sometimes mood stabilizers are used with antidepressants to treat depression.

Eg; lithium, valproic acid

Antipsychotic medications. Antipsychotic drugs are typically used to treat psychotic disorders, such as schizophrenia. Antipsychotic medications may also be used to treat bipolar disorders or used with antidepressants to treat depression.

Eg; Haloperidol, risperidone, quetiapine, aripiprazole

Self-help: A person coping with a mental health condition may decide to make certain lifestyle changes to help them manage their well-being. Changes may include trusted Source.

- reducing alcohol intake, if applicable
- trying to improve sleep quality
- eating a balanced, nutritious diet
- taking time away from work, if this is possible

- practicing relaxation techniques, such as deep breathing, meditation, and mindfulness

Objectives:

General Objective:

To assess the drug related problems in in-patients with Psychiatric disorders.

Specific Objectives:

- To assess the drug utilization pattern amongst psychiatric patients.
- To determine the nature, pattern and incidence of drug related problems.
- To monitor and manage the identified Adverse drug reactions (ADR).
- To identify the risk factors associated with the development of DRPs among the study population.

Review of literature

- Anjali Jayakumar et al. conducted a controlled intervention study to detect the frequency of Drug Related Problems (DRPs) frequently take place in modern medical practices, increasing the morbidity and mortality as well as the cost of patient care. The current study was undertaken to identify and evaluate various DRPs among the in patients of the psychiatry department in a tertiary care teaching hospital using APS- Doc classification system and to identify the most recurrent drugs causing the DRPs. It is a prospective observational study was conducted for duration of six months among 198 patients using APS-Doc classification system. The data was statistically analysed. A total of 205 DRPs were identified in 102 patients, among which 115 (56.1%) were potential drug-drug interactions (pDDI) and 62 (30.2%) were adverse drug reactions (ADRs). 21 (10.2%) DRPs belonged to the category of incorrect spelling of the trade name and 3 (1.5%) among them belonged to unintended prescription of the same drug. Two out of 205 DRPs (1%) belonged to the class of prescription of an incorrect dosage form or no dosage

prescribed. One DRP each were categorised under wrong dosage form prescribed and inadequate generic substitution respectively. Out of the total of 314 drugs, risperidone (n = 43, 13.7%) was found to be the drug associated with the greatest number of DRPs followed by olanzapine (n = 38, 12.1%) and lorazepam (n = 32, 10.2%). The study revealed that more than half (51.5%) of the patients presented with DRPs and the most commonly identified DRPs were pDDIs and ADRs.

- Sarfaraz Mohammed et al. conducted a study to identify DRPs, drug classes involved in DRPs as well as associated factors with the occurrence of DRPs and to assess the pharmacist interventions in a tertiary care hospital. A prospective observational study was carried out in a tertiary care teaching hospital, over a period of 6-month from November 2015 to April 2016. All the in patients admitted to all departments of hospital, who satisfied the selection criteria, were included in this study. Necessary demographic and clinical data were collected from the case records. The Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Classification Version 5.01 was used to classify DRPs. The treatment data were analyzed to determine the rate, pattern, clinical significance, and outcomes of DRPs. A total of 300 patient case sheets were reviewed during the study, out of which 143 DRPs were identified from 93 patients. Male (%) predominance was noted over females (%). The most common DRP was drug interactions 47.55% (68) followed by drug use problems 19.58% (28), drug choice problems 14.68% (21), others 11.88% (17), dosing problems 4.89% (7), and adverse reaction 1.39% (2) were identified. DRPs are common among the wards of hospital. Clinical pharmacist's role in identification, resolution, and prevention of DRPs helps in achieving better therapeutic outcomes and improved patient healthcare.

- Ephrem Mebratu Dagne et al. conducted study to determine the prevalence of drug-related problems and the factors influencing them among adult psychiatric inpatients. A multi-centre cross-sectional observational study was conducted from April to July 2021 at five randomly selected hospitals in Northwest Ethiopia. A total of 325 consecutively sampled patients participated in the study. Clinical pharmacists assessed the drug-related problems based

on clinical judgement supported by updated evidence-based disease guidelines. We used the Medscape drug-interactions checker to check drug-to-drug interactions. The results were summarised using descriptive statistics, including frequency, mean, and standard deviation. For each variable, an odds ratio with a 95% confidence interval was calculated, as well as the related p-value. The value of $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. From the total number of 325 study participants, more than half of them (52.9%) were females, and the mean age \pm (standard deviation) was 30.8 ± 11.3 years. At least one drug-related problem was recorded by 60.9% to 95% confidence interval (55.7–65.8) of study participants, with a mean of 0.6 ± 0.49 per patient. Additional drug therapy was the most common drug-related problem (22.8%) followed by non-adherence to medicine (20.6%) and adverse drug reactions (11%), respectively. Factors independent associated with drug-related problems were rural residence (adjusted odds ratio = 1.96, 95% confidence interval: 1.01–2.84, p-value = 0.046), self-employed (adjusted odds ratio = 6.0, 95% confidence interval: 1.0–36.9, p-value = 0.035) and alcohol drinkers (adjusted odds ratio = 6.40, 95% confidence interval: 1.12–37.5, p-value = 0.034). The prevalence of drug-related problems among adult psychiatric patients admitted to psychiatric wards was high. Healthcare providers give more attention to tackling these problems. Being a rural resident, self-employed, and alcohol drinkers were associated with drug-related problems.

- Goitom Mengistu et al. study was aimed to determine prevalence of drug related problems and identify associated factors among psychiatric patients admitted to psychiatric ward of Jimma University Medical Center; Jimma, Southwest Ethiopia; 2018. Method: A hospital based prospective observational study was conducted among psychiatric patients admitted to Jimma University Medical Center from March 01 to August 30, 2018. A structured data collection tool was used to collect patient's specific data. Bivariate and multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify the associated factors of drug related problems. Result: A total of 135 study participants were included for analysis. Among the total in 100(74.1%) patients developed drug related problems. The average number of drug related problems were 1.61. The most commonly

identified drug related problems, were need additional drug therapy 51(31.7%), ineffective drug therapy 35(21.7%), and adverse drug reactions 30 (18.6%). Factors independently associated with drug related problems were duration of treatment (>3 years) (AOR=18.2, 95% CI; 2.0-62.0), cigarette smoking (AOR=6.8, CI; 1.1-42.4), and polypharmacy (AOR=8.84, 95% CI; 1.46-23.5). Participants who resided in rural area had 68% lower than from those who resided in urban area (AOR=0.32, 95%CI; 0.10-0.98). Conclusion and recommendation: Drug related problems were considerable among admitted psychiatric patient. Initiation of additional drug therapy, ineffective drug therapy, and adverse drug reactions were commonly identified drug related problems. In response to this finding, tailored future intervention that target in prevention and resolution of those problems could be vital.

- Mateti et al. conducted a study on "Assessment of drug-related problems in depressive patients", the authors explored the incidence, causes, and preventability of drug-related problems (DRPs) among patients admitted to a psychiatric hospital. Their research, a prospective observational study over four months at Baliga psychiatric hospital in Udupi, involved 120 patients and aimed to uncover adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and potential drug-drug interactions (pDDIs) among those treated for depression. Using tools like the Drug Reax-Micromedex database and Naranjo's algorithm, the study found a 15.83% incidence of DRPs, with women and individuals aged 40–60 being particularly affected. The most frequently involved medications were sertraline, amitriptyline, and lithium, with hyponatremia and headache as common ADRs. Notably, 76.92% of ADRs were assessed as probable, mild, and definitely preventable. The study emphasizes the vulnerability of depressive patients to DRPs due to factors like age, gender, polypharmacy, and psychiatric comorbidities that can alter drug metabolism. It calls for the implementation of standardized monitoring programs and highlights the essential role of pharmacists in identifying and managing DRPs to enhance patient safety and reduce healthcare costs. The authors conclude by advocating for interventional research and pharmaceutical care strategies to mitigate DRP risks, pointing to the need

for systemic changes in psychiatric pharmacotherapy to improve clinical outcomes.

- Karina Porsborg Kibsdal et al. in the year 2020 investigated the rates and correlates of pharmacotherapy-related problems among psychiatric inpatients in Denmark, addressing a critical gap in understanding drug-related problems (DRPs) within psychiatric care. The authors conducted a retrospective descriptive study using data from 607 medical reviews performed in two psychiatric wards in Northern Jutland from June 2015 to February 2017, identifying a total of 1,385 DRPs, with an average of 2.5 DRPs per medication review. The most frequently observed categories of DRPs were drug dosage (19.9%), inappropriate drug (16.3%), interactions (15.6%), and side effects (11.8%), cumulatively representing over 60% of all DRPs. A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.811$) was found between the number of prescribed drugs and the frequency of DRPs, with psycholeptics, psychoanaleptics, and drugs for acid-related disorders being the most implicated, particularly olanzapine, quetiapine, and pantoprazole. Despite the high prevalence, only 49% of the CPs' intervention recommendations were accepted, and 33% were implemented. The study underscores the significance of involving clinical pharmacists (CPs) in psychiatric medication management, showing their ability to identify a wide range of DRPs and suggesting that structured medication reviews could significantly enhance patient safety and treatment outcomes. The authors highlighted various systemic factors influencing the acceptance and implementation of pharmacist interventions, including communication methods, relationship dynamics with physicians, and institutional familiarity with CPs.

- Importantly, many DRPs involved somatic medications, indicating a need for greater interdisciplinary knowledge in psychiatric settings. Their findings also aligned with international literature suggesting that DRPs are common across healthcare systems but are especially prevalent in psychiatric populations due to complex polypharmacy and comorbidities. The study concluded that integrating CPs into psychiatric care teams and promoting regular medication reviews could be instrumental in reducing preventable DRPs,

improving pharmacotherapy quality, and enhancing patient safety. Despite limitations such as lack of generalizability and the CPs' initial unfamiliarity with psychiatric cases, the study offered pioneering evidence for the implementation of clinical pharmacy services in Danish psychiatric hospitals and called for broader awareness, further training, and improved collaboration across disciplines to mitigate DRP risks in vulnerable psychiatric patients.

- Liu et al. conducted a retrospective study in a Chinese tertiary hospital to investigate the prevalence and types of drug-related problems (DRPs) among hospitalized PD patients. Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative condition commonly affecting the elderly and is often associated with a complex medication regimen due to comorbidities. The study involved 209 inpatients and identified 274 DRPs, affecting 83.3% of patients with an average of 1.31 DRPs per patient. Using the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) classification version 8.03, the most frequent DRP was "unnecessary drug treatment" (59.1%), primarily resulting from the use of drugs without indication. Drug selection issues (81.8%) and dosing problems (14.6%) were identified as the primary causes, with traditional Chinese medicine injections and neurotrophic agents being the most frequently implicated drugs. Notably, 14.6% of the DRPs were severe enough to cause actual harm (categories E–H, per NCC MERP classification), emphasizing the clinical relevance of these issues. Comparative studies, such as Schröder et al. (2011), also found high DRP rates in PD outpatients, though methodological differences make direct comparisons difficult. Ali et al. (2018) demonstrated similar findings in neurology wards, highlighting the importance of clinical pharmacists in reducing DRPs. Likewise, Abunahlah et al. (2018) reported DRP rates above 80% in internal medicine wards, supporting the global prevalence of these issues. Liu et al. advocate for the integration of clinical pharmacists in neurology departments to improve drug therapy outcomes. Their findings underscore the critical need for targeted pharmaceutical care to enhance medication safety and optimize therapeutic outcomes for PD patients.

- Wali et al. conducted a prospective observational study to evaluate the impact of clinical

pharmacists in monitoring drug-related problems (DRPs) among psychiatric patients admitted to a tertiary care teaching hospital in Belagavi, Karnataka. The study enrolled 120 psychiatric patients over six months, with individuals aged over 18 years and diagnosed with psychiatric disorders such as bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, depression, and mania. The researchers aimed to identify, assess, and resolve DRPs, which are defined as events or circumstances related to drug therapy that potentially interfere with optimal patient outcomes. Utilizing Cipolle's classification system, they categorized DRPs into five main types: adverse drug reactions (ADRs), drug-drug interactions, overdose, sub-therapeutic dosage, and failure to receive medication. Among the participants, the most frequent DRP was ADRs (44.4%), followed by overdose (22.2%), with each of the remaining categories accounting for 11.1% of DRPs. A variety of psychotropic drugs were implicated, including lithium carbonate, olanzapine, risperidone, and sertraline. The Naranjo ADR probability scale and Hartwig's severity assessment scale revealed that most ADRs were classified as "possible" in terms of causality and were mild in severity, not requiring significant alteration in therapy. Notably, 103 interventions were proposed by the clinical pharmacists, with a 52.4% acceptance rate by attending psychiatrists. Many interventions suggested changes in drug dose or form, addition or cessation of medications, and modifications in administration route or frequency. The study demonstrated that clinical pharmacists played a vital role in identifying and resolving DRPs, thus enhancing therapeutic outcomes and reducing risks associated with pharmacotherapy in psychiatric settings. Supporting evidence from related studies reinforced these findings; for example, Canales et al. reported improved clinical responses and reduced drug-induced side effects among patients receiving intensive psychiatric pharmacy services, while Ramesh et al. found high acceptance rates for pharmacist interventions in managing DRPs in stroke patients. The authors also highlighted that the majority of DRPs were associated with antipsychotics and antidepressants, indicating the complexity and risks inherent in psychiatric pharmacotherapy. Despite some physicians being hesitant to act on pharmacist recommendations immediately, possibly due to perceived insignificance or clinical

conservatism, the study underscored the necessity of interdisciplinary collaboration. Ultimately, Wali et al. concluded that clinical pharmacists are an integral component of the healthcare team in psychiatric care, with a critical responsibility to minimize DRPs, thereby reducing comorbidities, healthcare costs, and hospital stays, while significantly improving patient care outcomes.

- Wien et al. conducted a comprehensive retrospective cohort study to evaluate the impact of implementing a computerized physician order entry (CPOE) system integrated with a clinical decision support system (CDSS), supported by hospital pharmacists, on the prevalence of drug-related problems (DRPs) in psychiatric inpatients at the Center for Integrative Psychiatry, Lübeck, Germany. Their investigation was driven by the high frequency of polypharmacy and the resultant DRPs commonly encountered in psychiatric care. Before the implementation of the digital system, prescriptions were handwritten and lacked real-time checks for drug interactions or dosage errors. The researchers reviewed medical records of two cohorts—54 patients before (cohort I) and 65 after (cohort II) the implementation. Using the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) Classification V9.1, along with DokuPIK and NCC MERP standards, 325 DRPs were identified in cohort I, equating to 151.9 DRPs per 1000 patient days, and 214 DRPs in cohort II, reducing the rate to 81.3 DRPs per 1000 patient days. The CPOE/CDSS system notably decreased erroneous prescriptions from 34.8% to 5.6% and reduced unsolved DRPs at discharge. Furthermore, the odds of encountering a DRP were significantly lower post-implementation (OR = 0.545, $p < 0.001$). Most DRPs involved psychotropic medications, particularly antidepressants and antipsychotics, with quetiapine being most frequently implicated. Additionally, nearly a third of DRPs in both groups were due to drug interactions, such as dangerous serotonergic combinations. The system's integration allowed pharmacists to validate prescriptions daily, leading to 61 interventions, of which 54.1% were accepted. Importantly, DRPs causing significant patient harm, including prolonged hospitalization or life-threatening events, were documented only in the pre-implementation cohort. Post-implementation, there was a marked decline in severe DRPs and

improved discharge safety, supported by employee feedback indicating that staff found the system useful and efficient. The study further analyzed anticholinergic burden using TDBAC, ACB, and DBIAC scores, revealing moderate but clinically relevant exposure levels in both cohorts. Overall, the study confirmed that CPOE systems with CDSS, when supplemented by pharmacist-led validation, effectively reduce DRPs, particularly prescribing errors, in psychiatric inpatients, although a fully interdisciplinary medication management strategy may be necessary to further minimize unsolved DRPs. The findings align with global healthcare safety initiatives and highlight the essential role of technological and pharmaceutical interventions in enhancing psychiatric medication safety.

- Samaksha et al. conducted a novel prospective interventional study focusing on the collaborative role of clinical pharmacists and psychiatrists in pharmacotherapy management among geriatric psychiatric patients, aiming to enhance therapeutic outcomes and reduce drug-related problems (DRPs). Conducted over six months in a tertiary care psychiatry outpatient department in Mysuru, India, the study enrolled 84 elderly patients, predominantly female and illiterate, with diagnoses including depression, bipolar affective disorder (BPAD), schizophrenia, and alcohol dependency syndrome (ADS). The study introduced a structured collaboration where clinical pharmacists conducted medication reviews, identified DRPs, and provided counseling and therapeutic suggestions, which were then discussed with psychiatrists. Pharmacists offered a total of 155 services across counseling, interventions, and drug information, averaging two services per patient. Notably, 48 interventions were made, with adverse drug reactions (47.91%) and drug-drug interactions (18.75%) being the most frequent issues addressed. About 77.08% of these interventions were accepted and led to therapy changes. The interventions predominantly held moderate clinical significance. Furthermore, 23 drug information services were documented, mainly concerning medication availability, interactions, and adverse effects, with psychiatrists and postgraduate trainees being primary recipients. The findings mirrored results from global literature highlighting the high incidence of DRPs in elderly psychiatric

patients due to polypharmacy and comorbidities. Comparative studies also showed similar acceptance rates and clinical impacts of pharmacist interventions. The most implicated drugs were antipsychotics and antidepressants, which are frequently associated with adverse reactions in elderly populations. This study emphasized the pivotal role of clinical pharmacists in geriatric psychiatry, demonstrating that their collaboration with psychiatrists not only improved medication safety and adherence but also reduced healthcare costs, length of hospital stay, and potentially enhanced the quality of life. Samaksha et al. concluded that structured, pharmacist-led pharmacotherapy management is crucial in identifying and resolving DRPs, thus advocating for its broader integration into geriatric mental healthcare settings in India.

- John et al. conducted a prospective, pre- and post-non-randomized interventional study examining the effectiveness of clinical pharmacist-led interventions in enhancing medication adherence and resolving drug-related problems (DRPs) among psychiatric patients prescribed selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs). Conducted at KLE's Dr. Prabhakar Kore Charitable Hospital in Belagavi, India, over six months, the study recruited 90 psychiatric patients over 18 years of age who were undergoing SSRI therapy. The researchers focused on two major concerns in psychiatric care: poor medication adherence and the occurrence of DRPs—both of which can severely hinder therapeutic success. Non-adherence, often caused by intentional or unintentional behaviors, such as forgetfulness, misunderstanding of medication instructions, or underestimating the need for continued therapy after symptom relief, is known to be particularly prevalent in psychiatric populations. At baseline, 56.7% of patients reported DRPs, with non-adherence significantly associated with these problems. Pharmacist-led interventions included patient education, counseling on medication use, and addressing lifestyle factors, all of which were aimed at optimizing therapeutic outcomes. As a result of these interventions, DRPs significantly declined to 28.9%, and adherence scores, measured using the MARS scale, showed substantial improvement post-intervention ($p = 0.03$). Notably, 70% of patients fully implemented the pharmacist's recommendations, and

a further 10% partially implemented them. The majority of DRPs were patient-related and primarily stemmed from inadequate understanding or discontinuation of medications without medical consultation. This aligns with earlier findings by Lucca et al., which emphasized the critical role of patient education in improving adherence. Furthermore, the study revealed significant correlations between levels of adherence and DRP frequency—those with high adherence had the lowest DRP incidence, while those with low or moderate adherence had significantly higher incidences. Adverse effects such as insomnia, a common issue in SSRI therapy, were frequently reported, consistent with data from earlier studies by Kostev et al. that highlight how side effects can contribute to treatment discontinuation. John et al. demonstrated that with structured interventions led by clinical pharmacists, it is possible to dramatically reduce these risks, promoting safer and more effective psychiatric care. The study supports the PCNE classification system for categorizing DRPs and underscores the importance of multidisciplinary care involving pharmacists in psychiatric settings. The authors concluded that integrating clinical pharmacists into psychiatric teams significantly contributes to medication adherence and minimizes preventable drug-related morbidity and mortality. This model, emphasizing continuous patient-pharmacist-psychiatrist interaction, holds substantial promise for enhancing the quality of life in individuals with mental health disorders and represents a scalable framework for healthcare systems seeking to improve psychotropic drug therapy outcomes.

- Hongthong et al. conducted a significant study assessing the cost-benefit of psychiatric pharmaceutical care integrated with shared decision-making (PPC-SDM) in complicated schizophrenic patients. The literature acknowledges that conventional psychiatric pharmaceutical care focuses on identifying and correcting drug-related problems (DRPs), but often lacks patient involvement, resulting in high readmission rates due to poor adherence and adverse drug reactions (ADRs). The authors emphasized shared decision-making (SDM) as a collaborative process, enabling patients to participate in treatment decisions, enhancing therapeutic adherence, and improving clinical outcomes. The

PPC-SDM model employed six structured steps, including patient education and continuous monitoring, and was implemented using the Integrated Hospital Medication Management System (IHoMe-SDM). Previous studies cited by the authors (Kanjanasilp & Ploylearmsang, 2016; Elwyn et al., 2012) supported that SDM improves patient understanding and medication compliance. Pharmacist-led SDM was shown to reduce medication errors and hospitalization due to ADEs. The study's literature review also referenced economic evaluations by Mutnick et al. (1997) and Gallagher et al. (2014), establishing frameworks for calculating cost savings and avoidance through clinical interventions.

- Kulchalee Deawjaroen et al. Conducted a study on Drug-related Problems and Pharmacist's Interventions in Hospitalized Patients in Thailand. provides a comprehensive examination of drug-related problems (DRPs) and the role of pharmacists in mitigating these issues in a hospital setting. DRPs are significant global concerns due to their potential to cause harm and increase healthcare costs. In response, the World Health Organization's Global Patient Safety Challenge aims to reduce medication-related harm by 50%. This study, conducted in a tertiary hospital in Northern Thailand, involved 257 hospitalized patients and identified 316 preventable DRPs. Notably, nearly half of the DRPs occurred at discharge, highlighting a critical point of vulnerability. The most frequent DRP was the omission of necessary drug therapy, accounting for 32.3% of cases and 56.1% at discharge. Other common issues included adverse drug events and incorrect dosages. Pharmacist interventions were integrated into daily patient care using tools like the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) classification and NCC MERP index for severity. The most common intervention was initiating omitted drug therapy, predominantly at the prescriber level, with a high acceptance rate of 95.8% by physicians. This indicates strong interprofessional collaboration. The study identified cardiovascular drugs, anti-infectives, and gastrointestinal agents—specifically atorvastatin, omeprazole, and warfarin—as frequently implicated in DRPs. It also emphasized stage-specific DRP patterns: renal function-related dose adjustments were prevalent during hospital stay, while drug

omissions were more common at discharge. Compared to previous studies by Garin et al. (2021), Blix et al. (2004), and Kaboli et al. (2006), which typically focused on DRPs at a single hospitalization point, this research provides a stage-wise analysis across admission, stay, and discharge.

- Ranković et al. investigated the prevalence, severity, and risk factors associated with potential drug–drug interactions (pDDIs) in psychiatric inpatients. Psychiatric patients frequently suffer from comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes, often leading to polypharmacy and an increased risk of pDDIs. Previous studies have identified age, number of medications, and comorbidities as major risk factors (Ahmad et al., 2015; Borges et al., 2017). The study highlighted that the average number of pDDIs per patient ranged from 5.9 to 8.5, depending on the database used (Medscape, Epocrates, or Lexicomp). Risk factors consistently identified included C- reactive protein levels, the number of pharmacological subgroups, prescribed drugs, and the use of antibiotics, antacids, and vitamins. Protective factors included patient age and presence of certain comorbidities like hypertension. Notably, Lexicomp detected the highest number of severe pDDIs, emphasizing the need for clinicians to consult multiple databases. The study supports a multidisciplinary approach to minimize risks, involving pharmacists, physicians, and nurses. This research contributes valuable insight into managing medication safety in psychiatric settings and emphasizes the critical role of pharmacovigilance in preventing adverse drug events.

- Carolin Wolf et al. conducted a prospective, controlled clinical trial evaluating the effectiveness of pharmacist-led medication reviews in a psychiatric hospital setting in Germany. The study addresses the rising concern of drug-related problems (DRPs) in psychiatric populations, who are particularly vulnerable due to polypharmacy, comorbidities, and adherence challenges. Previous research by Procyshyn et al. (2010), Mann et al. (2008), and Rothschild et al. (2007) highlighted the high incidence of adverse drug events (ADEs) in psychiatric care, emphasizing the need for systemic interventions. Wolf's study implemented structured pharmacist-led medication reviews integrated with

interdisciplinary team discussions. Using the Medication Appropriateness Index (MAI) and Problem-Intervention-Outcome (PIO) classification based on PCNE criteria, the team systematically identified, resolved, and tracked DRPs. Patients receiving pharmacist interventions had a 1.4-point improvement in MAI scores at discharge and a 1.2-point improvement at the three-month follow-up. Additionally, these patients had 1.8 fewer unsolved DRPs per person compared to the control group. The high recommendation acceptance rate (88.6%) further emphasized the effectiveness of collaborative models involving clinical pharmacists. Psychotropic medications such as quetiapine and venlafaxine were frequently involved in DRPs due to inappropriate dosing and inadequate monitoring—issues also highlighted by Grasso et al. (2003) and Keers et al. (2014). This reflects the critical need for systematic medication reviews in psychiatry, where therapeutic complexity increases the risk of medication errors. The findings align with prior studies by Viktil and Blix (2008) and Graabaek and Kjeldsen (2013), who reported similar benefits of pharmacist interventions in internal medicine and geriatric settings. Moreover, the study supports guidelines from the American Psychiatric Association (2003), advocating for structured approaches to enhance medication safety. Although limited by its non-randomized design and single-institution setting, the longitudinal approach and use of validated tools like the MAI lend credibility to the results. Unlike earlier studies by Alderman (1997) and Dolder et al. (2008), this trial offers a more rigorous evaluation of pharmacist interventions.

- Matthew Syrnyk et al. Conducted a study on pharmacist interventions in medication adherence in patients with mental health disorders. Medication adherence in patients with mental health disorders continues to be a critical issue, often influenced by a combination of illness-related, medication-related, and psychosocial factors such as depression, cognitive impairment, side effects, stigma, and lack of insight into illness, as discussed by Syrnyk and Glass (2023). Their scoping review aimed to explore the breadth of pharmacist-led interventions targeted at improving adherence in this vulnerable population. The review included 11 studies from diverse settings—community pharmacies, hospitals, and

interdisciplinary mental health clinics—spanning retrospective cohort studies, quality improvement projects, and service evaluations. Key findings suggest that pharmacists play a significant role at transitions of care, via digital health platforms, and through structured medication counseling and follow-up. For instance, Barrett et al. (2020) and McMillian et al. (2018) found that pharmacist interventions involving motivational interviewing and shared decision-making significantly enhanced medication adherence and patient satisfaction. Furthermore, Bingham et al. (2020) highlighted that pharmacist telehealth services led to improved proportion of days covered (PDC) for psychotropic medications. According to Wright et al. (2016), pharmacists embedded within mental health clinics not only increased adherence rates but also contributed to reduced hospitalization and emergency department visits, reflecting economic as well as clinical benefits. Similarly, Herbert et al. (2018) demonstrated that pharmacists using structured assessment tools such as the PHQ-9 provided evidence-based recommendations and closer monitoring, resulting in improved treatment outcomes. The review also emphasized the importance of specialized training and credentialing, like the Board-Certified Psychiatric Pharmacist (BCPP) certification, to equip pharmacists with the skills necessary for psychiatric care, especially as a global shortage of psychiatrists looms (Syrnyk & Glass, 2023). Patient-centered approaches, including addressing patient beliefs, regimen complexity, and practical barriers like forgetfulness, were also found to be crucial enablers for adherence. Notably, interventions that involved patient perspectives, education, and tailored support plans yielded significant improvements in both adherence and perceptions of illness, as demonstrated by Klang et al. (2015) and Zmoira et al. (2021). Overall, this literature underscores the expanding role of pharmacists in mental health care, advocating for their integration into multidisciplinary teams to optimize psychotropic use and ultimately improve patient outcomes and system-level efficiency.

- Babelghaith et al. explored the incidence of DRPs and evaluated the impact of pharmacist interventions. The retrospective study, conducted from 2016 to 2017, identified 369 DRPs across inpatient departments, with serious drug-drug

interactions (DDIs) being the most common (49%), followed by prolonged antimicrobial therapy (33.3%). The authors found that pharmacist interventions were highly effective, with 78% of the recommendations accepted by physicians, resulting in changes to drug therapy. Notably, antibiotics were the most frequently implicated drug class, accounting for over half of all DRPs. This aligns with findings from Albadr et al. (2014), who also identified a high prevalence of DDIs related to antibiotics in internal medicine wards. Babelghaith et al. highlighted the crucial role of clinical pharmacists in minimizing DRPs through timely identification and intervention. The study also revealed discrepancies in physician acceptance rates across departments, suggesting institutional and interpersonal barriers to collaborative pharmaceutical care. These findings support earlier studies by Al Rahbi et al. (2014) and Molino et al. (2014), which emphasized the significance of pharmacist-led interventions in reducing prescribing errors and enhancing medication safety. Additionally, the observed reduction in DRPs over the two-year period suggests that sustained pharmacist involvement can have a measurable impact on patient outcomes.

- Shalansky et al. conducted a comparative study to evaluate the effectiveness of Pharmaceutical Care (PC) versus traditional clinical pharmacy monitoring in identifying and resolving drug-related problems (DRPs). Implemented in two general medicine wards, the study maintained constant staffing and monitoring time across both eight-week phases. During the PC phase, although fewer patients were monitored per shift, significantly more DRPs were identified (8.63 vs. 6.75; $p = 0.04$) and resolved (7.79 vs. 5.92; $p = 0.025$). The authors attributed this improvement to the comprehensive and patient-centered nature of PC, which involved more thorough patient assessment and engagement. Interestingly, while PC uncovered more DRPs of lower severity—mainly counselling and untreated indications—it did not result in clear cost advantages due to high variability in drug-related expenses. Despite the increased efficiency of DRP identification, the study acknowledges that further research is necessary to confirm whether PC positively impacts overall patient outcomes. This pivotal work supports PC as a valuable model in clinical pharmacy, particularly for

enhancing patient safety and individualized care without additional staffing resources.

- Zizzi et al. explored the psychological dimensions associated with Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD), comparing active drinkers to abstinent individuals. The study assessed 150 patients using validated psychometric tools to measure depression, hopelessness, impulsivity, and alexithymia. Results showed that active drinkers exhibited significantly higher levels across all these psychological domains compared to those who were abstinent. The authors emphasized that impulsivity and alexithymia not only contribute to the development and maintenance of AUD but also predict relapse and hinder treatment outcomes. Depression and hopelessness, common among active drinkers, were linked to an increased risk of suicide and negatively affected the likelihood of recovery. The findings support the notion that abstinence plays a pivotal role in reducing psychological distress and enhancing mental well-being in individuals with AUD. The authors conclude that comprehensive, personalized interventions targeting these psychological factors are crucial for long-term recovery. This study underscores the necessity of integrating psychological care into AUD treatment plans and highlights the importance of abstinence in preventing both mental health deterioration and life-threatening consequences such as suicide.

- Eshiet et al. investigated the impact of clinical pharmacists in identifying and resolving drug-related problems (DRPs) among epilepsy patients in Nigeria. The study, conducted across two major epilepsy referral centers, involved 95 participants and employed the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Classification Scheme V8.02. A total of 277 DRPs were recorded, with 57% being patient-related. Clinical pharmacists implemented 379 interventions, most of which involved direct patient engagement such as counseling, education on drug adherence, and medication storage. Approximately 62% of DRPs were fully resolved, and over half of the interventions were accepted and executed by prescribers and patients. The study underscored the effectiveness of pharmaceutical care (PC) in enhancing medication safety and therapeutic outcomes for people with epilepsy. Importantly, the findings highlight the

evolving role of pharmacists from traditional dispensing to integral members of healthcare teams, especially in under-resourced settings where specialized care is often limited. The authors emphasized the need for routine pharmacist-led medication reviews and collaborative therapeutic planning to minimize DRPs and improve patient outcomes.

- Alshaikhmubarak et al. Conducted a study on drug-related problems (DRPs) in hospital-based mental health units represent a critical and underexplored area of patient safety research. The author defined DRPs as events or circumstances involving drug therapy that interfere with desired health outcomes, and highlighted their frequent occurrence in psychiatric settings, often resulting in adverse drug events (ADEs), medication errors (MEs), and potentially inappropriate prescribing (PIP). The systematic review explored 22 studies, mostly conducted in Europe, which identified a variety of patient, medication, and hospital-related risk factors contributing to DRPs. Among the most consistently reported factors was polypharmacy, or the increased number of prescribed medications, which was significantly associated with a higher incidence of DRPs. Other patient-related risk factors included advanced age, cognitive impairment, and psychiatric comorbidities, while institutional factors such as hospitalisation duration and care setting differences also contributed to the risk. Alshaikhmubarak noted that mental health settings pose unique challenges due to the chronic nature of psychiatric illnesses and the long-term use of psychotropic medications, which are often prescribed at high doses. The review revealed that although several reviews have assessed the prevalence of DRPs, few have systematically investigated the specific risk factors, particularly in psychiatric hospitals. As a result, there exists a substantial gap in standardized approaches to identify high-risk patients and mitigate DRPs effectively. Alshaikhmubarak argued that the identification of such risk factors is essential for the development of pharmaceutical prioritization tools and clinical interventions aimed at enhancing medication safety. Furthermore, the review found that the use of robust statistical methods, such as multivariable logistic regression, was common in assessing associations between risk factors and DRPs,

though some studies lacked rigorous methodology or did not test for statistical assumptions. Ultimately, Alshaikhmubarak concluded that comprehensive and standardized assessment of DRP risk factors could inform targeted interventions, contributing to safer, more efficient psychiatric care. This review underscores the urgent need for continued research and healthcare policy improvements to minimize preventable medication harm in vulnerable inpatient populations.

Methodology

Study site:

The study was conducted in the psychiatry department of JSS Hospital, Mysuru. It is an 1800 bed multi-specialty tertiary care teaching hospital that provides healthcare facilities to people in and around Mysore district. The psychiatry department consists of 2 general units with OPD duties and on an average 35-40 patients are being treated everyday under the various specialty clinics including family therapy clinic, de-addiction clinic, memory clinic, sexual medicine clinic, child guidance clinic under the supervision of expert psychiatrist, psychologist and social workers. De-addiction clinic provides both pharmacological and psychological therapy including motivational enhancement training, craving management training, cognitive behavioral therapy for the substance users by the specialized psychiatric healthcare professionals.

Study design:

This was a prospective interventional study.

Study period:

This study was conducted over a period of nine months.

Institutional Human Ethic Committee (IEC) Apprval:

The study was approved by the institutional Human Ethics Committee of JSS Medical College & Hospital, JSS AHER, Mysuru.

Study criteria:

- Naranjo adverse drug reaction probability scale

Inclusion criteria:

- Inpatients of any age of any gender who are admitted to psychiatric ward.
- Inpatients who are receiving at least two drugs.

Exclusion criteria:

- Inpatients who are non-co-operative, non-consenting and non-communicative.
- Patient who receives less than two drugs.

Sources of data:

All relevant and necessary data were collected from:

- Patient's case notes
- Patient's treatment charts
- Interaction with healthcare professionals
- Patient and/or patient caretaker interviews
- Patient's discharge summaries

Study Tools:

- Hepler and strand's classification of drug related problems
- WHO core prescribing indicators
- Lexicomp (UpToDate) drug interaction checker
- Micromedex
- Medscape
- WHO-UMC causality assessment system

Study Procedure**Design & process of informed consent:**

An informed consent form was designed incorporating all the vital information about the study. An informed consent form, written in English and translated into Kannada, was used to find out the patient's interest to participate in the study. Patients who met the study's requirements were added after giving their informed consent. Depending on patient convenience, both ICF versions were utilized by the study population. The informed consent form contains the details about the name of the study, the investigators involved, the study objective, study procedure, and the patient's voluntary agreement to participate. Those patients who were illiterate, the study were discussed with them and consent was obtained from caretakers.

Design of Data Collection Form (DCF):

A data collection form was developed and implemented for the collection and documentation of all the required data. The developed data collection form consists of various sections for data collection:

- Demographic details section consists of patient I.P No, age, weight, gender, date of admission & date of discharge.
- Clinical details including past medical history, allergy status, social history, diagnosis, lab investigations & treatment charts.
- A soft copy of the data collecting form was created using a Microsoft excel for recording, storing, accessing and analyzing the data.

Flow of the study

Objective 1: To assess the drug utilization pattern among Psychiatric patients

Prescriptions and treatment histories for each study participant were reviewed and recorded. The data was examined for the purpose to identify the number of medications that were used to treat the patient's illness. The pattern of drug use was examined using the WHO core prescription indicators.

WHO core prescribing indicators

Core prescribing indicators have been developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) to assess the quality of drug prescription practices

1. The average number of drugs per encounter:

The purpose is to identify poly-pharmacy. It was calculated by dividing the total number of drug prescribed by total number of patient encounters.

- Average number of drugs per encounter = Total no. of drugs prescribed/ Total clinical encounters

WHO Reference range = <2

2. The percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name:

To measure the tendency to prescribe by generic name. To promote cost effective prescribing and availability. It was calculated by dividing the number of drugs prescribed by generic name by the total number of drugs prescribed, multiplied by 100 and expressed as a percentage.

Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name =

$$\frac{\text{Total number of drugs prescribed by generic name}}{\text{Total number of drugs prescribed}} * 100$$

WHO Reference range = 100%

3. The percentage encounters with an antibiotic prescribed: It was used to monitor the overuse or misuse of an antibiotics. It was calculated by dividing the number of patient encounters in which an antibiotic was prescribed by the total number of drugs encounters, multiplied by 100 and expressed as a percentage.

Percentage of encounters with an antibiotics prescribed = $\frac{\text{Number of encounters with antibiotic prescribed}}{\text{Total number of encounters}} * 100$

WHO Reference range = $\leq 30\%$

4. The percentage encounters with an injection prescribed:

It was calculated to ensure the safe and rational use of injections. It was calculated by dividing the number of patient encounters in which an injection was prescribed by the total number of encounters, multiplied by 100 and expressed as a percentage.

Percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed = $\frac{\text{Number of injectable form of medicine prescribed}}{\text{Total number of medicines prescribed}} * 100$

WHO Reference range = $\leq 10\%$

5. The percentage of drugs prescribe from an essential drug list:

It was calculated to measure the degree to which practices conform to drug use as per the essential medication list. It was calculated by dividing the number of drugs prescribed which are in essential drug list by the total number of drugs prescribed, multiplied by 100 and expressed as a percentage.

- Percentage of drugs prescribed from essential medication list (EML) =

Number of medicines prescribed from the EDL/Total number of medicines prescribed * 100

WHO Reference range = 100%

Objective 2: To determine the nature, pattern and incidence of drug related problems

The researcher reviewed the treatment plans to find any problems related to drugs (DRPs). When these DRPs were discovered, they were reported to the suitable medical practitioner so that necessary action could be taken. The following criteria were then used to classify the detected DRP using the Hepler and Strand classification approach.

The identified DRPs were categorised as per Hepler and strand's classification as follows:

- Untreated indication
- Drug use without indication
- Adverse drug reaction
- Drug drug interaction
- Subtherapeutic dose
- Overdose
- Improper drug selection
- Failure to receive drug

Using data from multiple drug resources, remedial actions were designed for identified drug-related issues. The relevant medical professionals were then informed of these recommendations for corrective measures. Both before and after the pharmacist's intervention, records that related to the medication therapy were documented. The Lexicomp drug interaction checker (UpToDate), which enables medical practitioners to evaluate possible drug interactions, was used to find drug interactions. A list of medications can be entered into the subscription-based checker to determine whether any known interactions exist between them.

The severity of each type of drug-drug interaction was further classified as

- Minor
- Moderate
- Major

Assessment of significance levels:

Expected clinical outcomes were used to assess the clinical significance of pharmacist interventions:

- Minor: Therapy changes that don't significantly affect clinical results, expenditure, or hospital stays.
- Moderate: Interventions that increase the efficacy of therapy while lowering treatment expenses or complications for patients.
- Major: Interventions aimed at addressing severe drug-related issues that might reduce hospital stays by at least 24 hours.

Figure 1: Determination of Nature, pattern and incidence of drug related problems

The incidence of drug related was calculated by:

Incidence of DRP = No. of DRPs/Total No. of patients

Objective 3: To monitor and manage the identified Adverse drug reaction (ADR):

In order to ensure the safety of patients and improve therapeutic outcomes, the goal is to carefully identify, assess, and manage adverse drug reactions. Continuous patient monitoring for indications of adverse drug reactions (ADRs), timely documenting and assessment of the reaction, quick clinical

intervention where required, and reporting to relevant pharmacovigilance systems are all part of this. This purpose aims to lower the occurrence and severity of adverse drug reactions (ADRs) while encouraging informed decisions in following treatment plans by placing together an effective approach.

A established method is used to properly monitor and manage the detected Adverse Drug Reaction (ADR)is as follows.

1. Documentation and Reporting:

- Include any relevant information about the adverse drug reaction (ADR) in the patient's medical records, including the drug name, dosage, response, onset, and severity.
- Inform the relevant pharmacovigilance authorities about the ADR (for example, through national programs, WHO-UMC, or MedWatch).

2. Assessment of the ADR:

- To determine causality, use created tools such as the Naranjo Algorithm.
- The WHO-UMC scale is used to assess the probability that a medicine may cause a reaction.

3. Clinical Management

- Stop using the suspected medication (if appropriate).
- Give supportive care, such as antihistamines for allergic responses.
- If necessary, start certain treatments or antidotes.
- Depending on how serious the ADR is, regularly check vital signs and test results.
- If further therapy is required, switch to other drugs.

4. Root Cause Analysis

- Check for potential drug interactions, risk factors specific to the patient (age, hepatic/renal function, allergies), and compliance.

5. Patient education and follow up

- Make sure the patient is aware of the ADR and its consequences.
- To avoid re-exposure in the future, record in an allergy card or profile.
- Arrange for follow-up phone calls or visits to track healing and make sure there are no adverse effects.

Objective 4: To identify the risk factors associated with the development of DRPs among the study population.

The objective of the study is to explore into and find possible risk factors that could lead to the investigation's sample developing Drug-Related Problems (DRPs). This involves investigating in patient adherence, drug interactions, poly-pharmacy, concurrent diseases, and demographic factors.

RESULTS

A prospective interventional study was done over a period of nine months on patients admitted to the Department of Psychiatry at JSS Hospital, Mysuru. During the study's duration, 276 patients were admitted to the study site, with 48 patients excluded and 228 were eligible and enrolled in the study. The findings were shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Study Participants

Patient Demographics:

Data on demographics such as age, gender, social habits and the number of co-morbid conditions, has been collected. Each eligible patient gave consent to be included in the study. Of the total 228 patients with

psychiatric disorder 168 (73.6%) were male and 60 (26.4%) were female. Male predominance was observed in the study. Patient aged 31-40 (42%), 41-50 (16%), 51-60 (18%) years were predominant in the population.

Table 1: Demographic details of the study population

Demographics		Number n (%) (N=228)
Gender	Male	168 (73.6%)
	Female	60 (26.4%)
Age group	11-20	9 (4%)
	21-30	28 (12%)
	31-40	95 (42%)
	41-50	37 (16%)
	51-60	41 (18%)
	61-70	16 (7%)
	71-80	2 (0.8%)
No. of co-morbid conditions	Present	59 (25%)
	Absent	169 (74%)
Social history	Present	91 (39.9%)
	Absent	137 (60.8%)

Number of co-morbidities among the study population:

Among the study population, there were 5 different comorbidities observed. They were Hypertension,

diabetes mellitus, anxiety, schizophrenia, gastrointestinal and insomnia problems. Of the study population, 25.87% reported having at least one comorbidity. Total 59 comorbidities were observed. Major co-morbid conditions observed during study

period was Hypertension [23(38.9%)] and Diabetes mellitus [17(28.8%)].

Table 2: Details of comorbid conditions of the study population

Comorbid Condition	Number of patients (n = 59)
Hypertension	23 (38.9%)
Diabetes mellitus	17 (28.8%)
Schizophrenia	7 (11.8%)
Anxiety	6 (10.1%)
Gastrointestinal problem	6 (10.1%)

Figure 3: Distribution of the number of comorbidities among the study population

Dual diagnosis among Psychiatric patients

Among the study population, the dual diagnosis was identified. The common dual diagnosis identified during the study period was Bipolar affective disorder & Alcohol dependence syndrome, Behavioural

disorder and alcohol dependence syndrome, Alcohol dependence syndrome & Nicotine dependence syndrome, Alcohol dependence syndrome & depression, Mania & cannabis dependence syndrome, Alcohol dependence syndrome & schizophrenia.

Table 3: Dual diagnosis in psychiatric patients (Psychiatric illness + Substance use)

Commonly observed dual diagnosis	Number of patients, (n = 38)
Behavioural disorder & ADS	13 (34.21%)
BPAD & ADS	8 (21.05%)
ADS & NDS	8 (21.05%)
ADS & schizophrenia	4 (10.52%)
Mania & Cannabis dependence syndrome	3 (7.89%)
ADS & depression	2 (5.26%)

Figure 4: Analysis of Dual Diagnosis among Individuals with Psychiatric Disorders

Objective 1 : To assess the drug utilisation pattern using WHO prescribing indicators amongst psychiatric patients:

Total number of drugs prescribed = 1777

1. Average number of drugs per encounter:

= Total no. of drugs prescribed/Total clinical encounters

= 1777/228

= 7.79

WHO reference range- <2

2. Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name:

= Total number of drugs prescribed by generic name/Total number of drugs prescribed *100

=158/1777*100

=8.8%

WHO reference range - 100%

3. Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed:

= Number of encounters with antibiotic prescribed/Total number of encounters

* 100

=29/228*100

= 12.7%

WHO reference range- <30%

4. Percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed:

= Number of injectable form of medicine prescribed/ Total number of medicines prescribed *100

=83/228*100

=36.40%

WHO reference range- <20%

5. Percentage of drugs prescribed from an essential drug list (EDL):

= Number of medicines prescribed from the EDL/Total number of medicines prescribed * 100

= 1359/1777 * 100

=76.4%

WHO reference range- <100%

Table 4: identified who prescribing indicators for the prescribed drugs

WHO prescribing indicators	Total No. Of drugs/ encounters	Observed value	WHO ideal value
Average number of drugs per encounters	1777	7.79	<2
Percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name	158	8.8%	100%
Percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed	29	12.7%	<30%
Percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed	83	36.40%	<20%
Percentage of drugs prescribed from an essential drug list	1359	76.47%	100%

Objective 2: To determine the nature, pattern and incidence of drug related problems

During the study period, 228 patients presented with a total of 265 drug-related problems (DRPs). It indicates that on an average each patient experienced 1.1 during their admission to the hospital. A total of 1771 drugs were prescribed to the patients during the

study period. The DRPs were classified according to the Hepler -strand's classification.

The majority of drug related problems identified during the study period was Drug interactions (58.8%), following were untreated indications at (13.2%). The below table describes the drug related problems in psychiatric patients as shown in the Table 5.

Table 5: Distribution of drug related problem among psychiatric patients

Type of Drug related problem	Number (n) = 265
Drug-drug Interaction	156 (58.86%)
Untreated Indication	35 (13.20%)
Adverse drug reaction	26 (9.81%)
Subtherapeutic dose	22 (8.30%)
Overdose	22 (8.30%)
Failure to receive drug	2 (0.75%)
Drug use without an indication	1 (0.37%)
Improper drug selection	1 (0.37%)

Figure 5: Most frequently occurring DRP

Untreated Indication:

Of the 265 Drug-Related Problems (DRPs) observed during the investigation, 35 (13.20%) were related to treatable indications. The untreated indications were anxiety, gastrointestinal tract problem (constipation, acidity), hallucination, nausea, cravings for smoking and Insomnia. The majority of untreated indications were found to be anxiety (8), followed by acidity (4), constipation (3), insomnia (3), body pain and headache (4).

Adverse drug reaction:

Among the 265 Drug-Related Problems (DRPs) reported during the study period, 26(9.81%) were found to have ADRs in individuals undergoing Mental health treatment. Constipation, drowsiness & nausea were the most frequently reported ADRs found. ADRs reported during the study period were evaluated for several characteristics, including cause, severity, preventability, and predictability of ADRs.

Drug-drug Interaction: Among 265 patients, 156 drug interactions were identified during a study period. Drug-drug interactions were identified using Lexicomp (UpToDate) drug interaction checker. The

incidence of drug interactions identified among the study population during study period was 68.42%. And drug interactions were categorised according to severity using the recommendations provided by Lexicomp drug interaction checker as follows: 63(40.38%) were identified as a minor, 76(48.71 %) as moderate and 17(10.89 %) as major interactions.

Incidence of RP was calculated by

➤ Incidence of DRP = No. of DRPs/Total No. of patients

$$= 156/228 = 0.68$$

Table 6: Distribution of Severity of Drug-drug interactions

Severity	Minor	63
	Moderate	76
	Major	17

The most commonly occurring interactions were reported by category, as indicated in the table below

Table 7: Most frequently occurring drug-drug interactions

Sl no.	Drug combination	Interaction	Intervention
1	Domperidone + Quetiapine	Quetiapine may enhance the QT prolongation effect of domperidone	Avoid combination
2	Risperidone + Domperidone	Quetiapine may enhance the QT prolongation effect of domperidone	Avoid combination
3	Disulfiram + Diazepam	Disulfiram may enhance the toxic effect of products containing ethanol (Diazepam)	Avoid combination
4	Flunarizine + Clonazepam	Clonazepam may enhance the CNS depressant effect of Flunarizine	Avoid combination
5	Clozapine + quetiapine	Quetiapine may enhance the constipating effect of clozapine	Monitor for signs of constipation
6	Risperidone + quetiapine	Quetiapine may enhance the CNS depressant effect of risperidone	Monitor for increased CNS depressant effect
7	Trihexyphenidyl + quetiapine	Trihexyphenidyl may increase the constipating effect of clozapine	Monitor for signs of constipation
8	Diclofenac + escitalopram	Escitalopram (SSRIs) may enhance the antiplatelet effect of Diclofenac (NSAIDs) because NSAIDs may diminish the therapeutic effect of SSRIs	Monitor for signs of increased bleeding risk
9	Lorazepam + sodium valproate	Valproate products may enhance serum concentration of lorazepam (Reduce the dose of lorazepam during coadministration with valproate products)	Monitor for signs of excessive sedation, drowsiness
10	Clozapine + quetiapine	Agents with clinically relevant anticholinergic effects (quetiapine) may enhance the constipating effect of clozapine	Monitor for signs of constipation
11	lithium + telmisartan, amlodipine, hydrochlorothiazide)	Thiazide and thiazide like diuretics may decrease the excretion of lithium	Monitor for signs of lithium Toxicity
12	Haloperidol+chlorpromazine	Chlorpromazine (QT prolonging miscellaneous agents) may enhance the QTc prolonging effect of haloperidol	Monitor for QTc prolongation

13	Lithium + Haloperidol	Lithium may enhance the neurotoxic effect of Haloperidol (Antipsychotic agents)	Monitor for signs of neurotoxicity, such as tremors, confusion
14	Olanzapine + Escitalopram	QT-Prolonging antipsychotics (olanzapine) may enhance the QTc-prolonging effect of QT prolonging antidepressants (escitalopram)	Monitor for QTc prolongation
15	Dapagliflozin + Quetiapine	Hyperglycemia associated agents may diminish the therapeutic effect of antidiabetic agents	Monitor blood glucose levels
16	Olanzapine + fluoxetine	Fluoxetine (serotonergic agents) may enhance the serotonergic effect of olanzapine(antipsychotic agents)	Monitor for signs of serotonin syndrome

Incidence of DRP was calculated by = No. of DRPs/Total No. of patients

=265/228

= 1.16

Objective 3: To monitor and manage the identified ADR

Among the 265 Drug-Related Problems (DRPs) documented during the study period, 26 (9.81%) were

identified to have ADRs in persons receiving mental health therapy.

Drugs most frequently implicated in ADRs

The most commonly implicated drugs in the reported ADRs were risperidone, quetiapine, oxazepam, carbamazepine, clonazepam, lorazepam and desvenlafaxine.

The details of the drugs implicated in ADRs are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Drugs implicated in the reported ADRs

Suspected drug(s)	No. of ADRs (%)	No. of patients who received drug	Incidence (No. of patients who experienced ADR/ No. of patients who received drug) x 100
Quetiapine	4 (15.38%)	95	4.2%
Risperidone	4(15.38%)	118	3.3%
Oxazepam	3 (11.53%)	62	4.8%
Carbamazepine	3 (11.53%)	25	12%
Lorazepam	2 (7.69%)	17	11.7
Clonazepam	2 (7.69%)	109	1.8%
Desvenlafaxine	2(7.69%)	28	7.1%
Lithium	1(3.84%)	44	2.2%
Budesonide & formoterol	1(3.84%)	4	25%
Clobazam	1(3.84%)	5	20%
Optineuron	1(3.84%)	63	1.5%
Haloperidol	1(3.84%)	23	4.3%
Clozapine	1(3.84%)	33	3%

Drug class included in the reported adverse drug reactions

Drug classes that cause ADRs were analyzed. Highest percentage of ADRs was noted with Antipsychotics (n=10, 38.46%) followed by benzodiazepines (n=7, 26.9%) and others

Figure 6: Assessment of ADRs based on class

Individual Reported ADRs

The most commonly identified ADR was constipation, Nausea & vomiting.

Table 9: Individual reported ADRs

Common ADRs observed	Number of ADRs
Constipation	6
Nausea	2
Blurred vision	2
Dizziness	2
Abdominal pain	2
Decreased appetite	2
Drowsiness	1
Dyspepsia	1
Rhinitis	1
Cough	1
Rash	1
Vomiting	1
Increased diastolic effect	1
Increased Alkaline phosphate	1
Diarrhoea	1
Fever	1

Causality Assessment of ADRs

The causal association between the suspected drug and the reported adverse reaction

was found to be 'probable' in 8 and 'possible' in 18 ADRs as assessed by using WHO probability scale. According to the Naranjo's algorithm 11 were probable and 15 were possible in their causality.

Figure 7: Causality assessment of the reported ADRs using WHO probability scale

Figure 8: Causality assessment of the reported ADRs using Naranjo's algorithm

Management of the reported ADRs

Of the total reported ADRs, suspected drug was withdrawn in 7 (26.92%) cases while in 10 (38.46%) were no change and dose was altered in 9(30.76%%) cases. No treatment was giving 8 patients and

symptomatic treatment given in 10 patients. The outcomes of the management of the reported ADRs were observed to be recovered in 16 and recovering was 4 and unknown was 1 and none of the ADRs were fatal. The details of the management of reported ADRs were shown in the table 10.

Table 10: Management of ADR

Management of ADRs	No. of ADRs
Fate of the suspected drug	
Dose altered	9(34.61%%)
Drug withdrawn	7 (26.92%)
No change	9(34.61%%)
Treatment given	
Specific	7 (26.92%)
Symptomatic	11 (42.30%)
No treatment	8 (30.76%)
Outcomes of ADRs	
Recovered	13 (50%)
Recovering	4 (15.38%)
Unknown	9 (34.61%)

Objective 4: To identify the risk factors associated with the development of DRPs among the study population.

Factors namely age; gender, drug-drug interactions, untreated indications and Adverse drug reactions

(ADRs) were analyzed to establish its association with drug related problems (DRPs). Chi-square test was used to determine the association between gender, age and comorbid conditions.

Table 11: Risk factors associated with DRPs

Variable		No. of patients	No. of patients with DRPs	Chi square	P value
Gender	Male	168	200	0.187	0.666
	Female	60	65		
Age	11-30	37	43	0.050	0.997
	31-50	132	152		
	51-70	57	68		
	71	2	2		
Co-morbid conditions	Yes	59	189	101.14	<0.0001
	No	169	76		
Social history	Yes	91	77	6.39	0.0115
	No	137	188		

DISCUSSION

According to the Pharmaceutical Care Network (PCNE), a 'Drug-Related Problem' is "an event or circumstance involving drug therapy that actually or potentially interferes with desired health outcomes. Hepler-strand classification was used to categorize DRPs. The study's findings highlight the high prevalence of drug-related problems (DRPs) among mental inpatients, underlining the important need for clinical pharmacist intervention and structured medication reviews in psychiatric settings. A total of 265 DRPs had been identified among 228 patients. There was a male predominance observed in our study [n=168, (73.6%)], while female was [n=60 (26.4%)]. The main reasons for the doctor's visit were alcohol dependence syndrome and bipolar affective illness, which were followed by other medical conditions. The age group most affected by psychiatric and associated DRPs falls within the age of 31-40 years. In our study, the average DRPs detected per patient was 1.1. Polypharmacy among the psychiatric population has a number of negative outcomes, including an increase in healthcare expenses and a higher risk of DRPs. Polypharmacy in psychiatric patients can also increase the risk of drug-drug interactions, especially between antipsychotic and other drugs like antidepressants and benzodiazepines etc. In terms of comorbid conditions, the most common comorbidity

seen in the study sample was hypertension, which was followed by diabetes. The most common type of DRP in our study was drug-drug interaction 58.86%, untreated indication 13.20% was the second most common type of DRP followed by ADR 9.81%. In our current study, most commonly used drugs were antipsychotics (496, 27.9%), benzodiazepines (298, 16.7%) & antidepressants (217, 12.2%). As a clinical pharmacist, addressing DRPs in mental patients is of vital importance for improved safety, improved effectiveness and polypharmacy management.

WHO prescribing indicators:

A number of variations from the ideal standards were found when the WHO prescription indicators were evaluated. A high degree of polypharmacy was indicated by the average number of medications each visit (7.79), which was much more than the WHO recommended value of fewer than 2. A bias for brand-name prescribing that could affect treatment costs and accessibility is shown by the fact that only 8.8% of the medications were given by their generic names, which is significantly less than the advised 100%. Rational use was demonstrated by the 12.7% of interactions with antibiotics that were prescribed, which was below the WHO-recommended range of less than 30%. Nevertheless, injectable prescriptions were used in 36.4% of interactions, which is more than the

recommended threshold of fewer than 20%. This raises questions regarding possible dangers connected with injectable usage. The essential drug list accounted for just 76.47% of prescribed medications, which is less than the 100% standard.

Drug related problems:

A total of 265 DRPs were identified in the present study. DRP observed in our study was 1.16 per patient. The most common DRP identified among study population was drug-drug interactions. Drug-drug interactions were categorized based on severity were identified as minor, moderate & major. Drug-drug interactions (DDIs), which make up 58.86 percent of all instances. This high percentage highlights how crucial it is to frequently examine drugs, particularly in conditions where polypharmacy is prevalent. According to research, 62.9% of hospitalized patients may have possible DDIs, with a significant proportion of those cases being moderately to moderately severe in severity. Lexicomp (UpToDate) and Micromedex are commonly used tools for evaluating and categorizing drug interactions based on their severity. These resources help pharmacists prioritize actions and avert serious problems. At 13.20%, untreated indications were the second most prevalent DRP, indicating gaps in starting required therapy. 9.81% of DRPs were adverse drug reactions (ADRs), which is consistent with research showing that ADRs are a major reason for hospital stays and ED visits. Overdosing and subtherapeutic doses were noted in 8.30% of instances each, suggesting difficulties in reaching ideal dosage schedules. Improper drug selection (0.37%), drug usage without indication (0.37%), and failure to receive medications (0.75%) were less common but clinically relevant problems. These results highlight the value of thorough medication management and the part clinical pharmacists play in identifying and dealing with DRPs to improve therapeutic results and patient safety.

These findings reflect the results of other studies in comparable contexts (e.g., Anjali Jayakumar et al., Sarfaraz Mohammed et al.).

ADR

Pharmacists utilize the Naranjo algorithm and the WHO-UMC causality scale to evaluate adverse drug

reactions. This awareness assists in the early detection of ADRs, such as constipation or sedation produced by antipsychotics and benzodiazepines, and ensures timely clinical interventions. Constipation was the most common ADR (n=6) of the 26 that were reported, followed by a number of other symptoms like nausea and impaired vision (each n=2). Sleepiness, rash, and increased alkaline phosphatase were less frequent adverse drug reactions (ADRs) (each n=1). The majority of reactions were mild to moderate, emphasizing the necessity of continuous observation to guarantee patient safety and treatment compliance. Coming to management of ADRs, Depending on the severity, ADRs were managed with dose modification (34.61%), medication withdrawal (26.72%), or no change (34.61%). The majority of treatment was symptomatic (42.30%), with some patients requiring no intervention (30.76%) and others having specialized therapy (26.92%). 34.61% of the patients' outcomes were unknown, 15.38% were still recuperating, and half of the patients healed completely, highlighting the importance of regular follow-up and documentation.

Risk factors

Coming to the risk factors Age and gender did not significantly correlate with DRPs ($P > 0.05$). DRPs were strongly and statistically significantly correlated with the presence of co-morbid conditions ($P < 0.0001$). DRPs were also substantially correlated with social history (e.g., drinking or smoking) ($P = 0.0115$). In general, social background and co-morbid diseases are important risk factors for DRPs in this population. The study emphasizes the critical role of clinical pharmacists in the detection, prevention, and resolution of drug-related problems. Pharmacist interventions, such as medication review, counseling, and prescriber communication, were essential for improving therapeutic results. This is consistent with global research demonstrating increased safety and shorter hospital stays with pharmacist-led treatment, as demonstrated by Kibsdal et al. and John et al. Pharmacists review patient treatment charts on a regular basis and consult with psychiatrists about therapy adjustments. Their treatments may include dose adjustments, drug withdrawal or substitution, and changes in delivery routes, all of which aim to optimize therapeutic outcomes while preventing

harm. Practical advantages, The incidence of preventable DRPs demands structured pharmaceutical care programs, routine medication reviews, the utilization of drug- interaction checkers such as Lexicomp, and enhanced use of evidence-based prescribing recommendations. Improved multidisciplinary teamwork among psychiatrists, pharmacists, and nursing personnel is critical for improving psychiatric patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Drug-drug interactions are the most frequent drug-related problem (DRP) among psychiatric inpatients, according to this study. With an average of 7.79 medications per patient. Particularly in the areas of generic prescribing and injectable use, a sizable percentage of prescriptions diverged from the optimal WHO prescribing parameters. The two medications most frequently linked to adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were benzodiazepines and antipsychotics. Frequent adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were drowsiness, nausea, and constipation; the majority were minor and treated symptomatically. DRPs were substantially correlated with risk factors such social background and co-morbidities. Clinical pharmacists are essential to enhancing medication safety and therapeutic results. The results highlight the significance of constant medication monitoring and rational prescription practices in mental health treatment.

Limitations

- Since the study was limited to mental hospital patients, drug-related problems were not evaluated in ambulatory settings or other wards.
- The sample size of our study small.

Future directions

- An identical study could be conducted in ambulatory settings.
- The study should be extended to the inpatient ward of neurology and geriatrics.
- Assist in improving the patient's health by lowering the risks of drug-related issues.

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